

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Value statement template

Actionable version

Definition

The Value Statement Template helps organisations identify and articulate the values that underpin their research assessment (RA) processes. Values define what is considered important and guide the choice of methods, materials and data used, and indicators. A clearly defined value statement is a starting point of a research assessment process.

This template provides a structured way to specify:

- Super-values (broad guiding principles, e.g., openness, diversity).
- Values (how super-values are expressed, e.g., diversity of careers).
- Sub-values (practical indicators, e.g., e.g., assessing performance relative to opportunities, like working as a reviewer).

Relevant SCOPE stages

This resource is most relevant in SCOPE stage:

- Start with what you value: Defining and prioritising values is the foundation of responsible evaluation.

It also informs later stages: options for evaluating (O), probe deeply (P), and evaluate your evaluation (E), since values guide decisions throughout the RA process.

When and how to use

Use this template when:

- Starting any research assessment process (e.g., recruitment, promotion, funding allocation).

How to use:

- Engage stakeholders (HR, researchers, leadership) to agree on shared values.
- List super-values (e.g., openness, inclusivity, quality).
- Translate super-values into values (e.g., inclusivity → diversity of careers and disciplines).
- Define sub-values with concrete examples (e.g., inclusivity → recognition of career breaks, multilingual publishing, mentoring)
- Document value statements in the provided template and use them as the basis for defining assessment criteria, metrics, and processes.
- Review and update periodically to reflect evolving priorities and practices.

Guidance

- Be explicit: Make values transparent and shared across the organisation.

- Balance breadth and detail: Use super-values for direction, values for clarity, and sub-values for practical implementation.
- Link values to indicators.
- Support cultural change: Values-based assessment helps move away from narrow metrics (e.g., journal impact factor) toward holistic evaluation.
- Engage collaboratively: Involve staff at all levels to ensure legitimacy and buy-in.

Further reading

SCOPE+i Resources

- Guide on choosing an assessment method:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721>
- Guide on equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) in research assessment:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526122>

Other

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- Science Europe (2023), Recognising What We Value:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7858100>

